

Statement of Intent on Open Research Europe

This Statement of Intent is signed by public research funding bodies, research performing organisations, and national ministries (hereinafter referred to as the ‘Signatories’) that are part of the Open Research Europe Interest Group. Together, the Signatories are committed to the development of [Open Research Europe](#) (ORE), an open access publishing platform with open peer-review.

This Statement reflects the intention of the Signatories to build a collectively funded Open Research Europe for the public good and in pursuit of more equity, diversity, and transparency in open access publishing. Presently, ORE is funded by the European Commission, allowing its grantees to publish without incurring author fees.

Vision for a collective ORE

The Signatories in collaboration with the European Commission intend to support and fund Open Research Europe as a collective, non-profit open access publishing service for an initial period of five years. ORE will remain an open access publishing platform with open peer-review. It will broaden its publishing eligibility criteria beyond European Commission-funded researchers. It will also progressively align with the diamond open access principles defined in the [‘Action Plan for Diamond Open Access’](#).

The Signatories share a common vision, outlined in the scoping report [‘Open Research Europe: Towards a Collective Open Access Publishing Service’](#). This vision, supported by Council Conclusions on open science and scholarly publishing from [2022](#) and [2023](#), is grounded in the following principles:

- Ensuring high-quality research and its integrity
- Maximising accessibility and usability
- Supporting an expanding range of contributions
- Community building
- A distributed, open infrastructure
- Equity, diversity & inclusivity
- Facilitating the evaluation of research
- Promoting flexibility & innovation
- Cost-effectiveness
- Accountability to the research community & the public

Guided by these principles, the Signatories in collaboration with the European Commission intend to actively participate in the governance of Open Research Europe, and contribute financially towards the operational costs and development of the platform.

The Signatories will engage with stakeholders from the research community to advance open access publishing for the public good, and make ORE accountable to research communities and the public.

The Signatories intend to specifically engage with researchers as the advisors, ambassadors, editors, authors, and reviewers that will make ORE a success.

Timeline and next steps

This Statement will be followed by a formal collaboration agreement between the Signatories, detailing the collective legal and governance structure, financial contributions, and operational framework and entity to operate ORE. The Signatories expect the official launch of the collectively managed and funded ORE platform by the end of 2026. The Signatories intend to evaluate the publishing platform, based on regular monitoring and evaluation exercises during the first five-year funding cycle.

Conclusion

This Statement signifies the intention of the Signatories to develop a collectively funded Open Research Europe, guided by the shared vision and principles mentioned in this document. The Signatories will work collectively and in collaboration with the European Commission towards the success of ORE as a publishing platform offering high quality and rigorous open access publishing services for researchers, ensuring its sustainability and alignment with the broader goals of equity, diversity, and inclusiveness in scholarly communication.

As of January 23th, 2025 the undersigned organisations endorse this Statement:

1. The Austrian Science Fund (FWF)
2. The Dutch Research Council (NWO)
3. The French National Research Agency (ANR)
4. The German Research Foundation (DFG)
5. The Research Council of Norway (RCN)
6. The Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)
7. The Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)
8. The Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)
9. The Swedish Research Council for Environment, Agricultural Sciences and Spatial Planning (FORMAS)
10. The Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (FORTE)
11. The Swedish Research Council (VR)